

polycaryoptic, indicating that WX154 and Double Rice have duplicate recessive genes for polycaryopsis (see table).

When the polycaryoptic line YA1, a selection from WX154/Tongilchal, was crossed with cytoplasmic male-sterile rice V20A, the F₁ was sterile. The F₁ was backcrossed to YA1. From this BCF₁, polycaryoptic male-sterile plants could be selected (see figure), showing that the polycaryoptic line YA1 is a maintainer for cytoplasmic male-sterility, and that polycaryoptic male-sterile plants selected could be maintained by successive backcrosses to YA1.

Polycaryoptic male-sterile rice may have greater seed set because it has four stigmas instead of two. The possibility of using this male-sterile rice for F₁ hybrid seed production is being explored. □

Polycaryoptic male-sterile (A), polycaryoptic fertile (B), and normal (C) rice.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Effect of abscisic acid on rice seedling resistance to chilling injury

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Rice seedlings Dansheng No. 1, Guichao No. 2, and Shanyou No. 2 were studied for the effects of abscisic acid (ABA) on resistance to chilling injury influenced by hormonal regulation.

ABA accumulation varied with varietal resistance to chilling injury. Five days after the low temperature (8-10°C) treatment, seedlings of cold-resistant Dansheng No. 1 showed an ABA increase over cold-sensitive Shanyou No. 2. The longer the

Change in ABA content in the leaves of Dansheng No. 1 during low temperature.

Days of low temperature	ABA content (ng/g fresh wt)
0	0.65
3	13.50
6	20.60
9	58.50
LSD	0.08

low temperature lasted, the more ABA accumulated in leaves of the seedlings (see table).

Exogenous application of ABA reduced the symptoms of chilling injury such as the leakage of electrolytes from leaves and roots (see figure), leaf discoloration, and reduction of leaf fresh weight. ABA accumulation response should be investigated in further studies. □

Effect of ABA on leakage of electrolytes in chilled rice seedlings.

Pest management and control DISEASES

Sheath rot in the Punjab, India

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Sheath rot (ShR) caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) Gam. was first reported in India in Hyderabad (A.P.) in 1974 and in Kapurthala (Punjab) in 1980. *Fusarium* has been associated with sheath and panicle rot of rice for the last 3 years,

particularly on variety PR106, but was ignored and considered a secondary invader.

Fusarium symptoms resemble those produced by *S. oryzae*. They are oblong or irregular spots, 5-20 mm long with